

THE INFLUENCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF LIVER CIRRHOSIS ON BLOOD COMPONENTS

A.M.Urinov

I.O.Otajonov

**Non-state educational university "Alfraganus",
Research Institute of Phthisiology and Pulmonology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10639759>**

Aim: identification of informative hemogram indicators when modeling liver cirrhosis

Materials and methods: Experimental studies were carried out on sexually mature laboratory animals obtained from the vivarium of the Central research laboratory of Tashkent medical academy.

Results: Cirrhosis is a liver disease with a progressive inflammatory mechanism, which leads to the development of fibrosis, as well as the development of concomitant diseases in the liver. To prevent the consequences of this pathology, timely diagnosis of the presence and severity of liver damage is of particular importance. Experimental studies on animals with a model of cirrhosis have proven that a high level of leukocytes and platelets is a diagnostic indicator for cirrhosis. The number of leukocytes increases in the group of experimental animals with liver damage by 115.57%, which is higher than the same figure among laboratory animals in the intact group and, accordingly, $6.10 \pm 0.29 \times 10$. The number of leukocytes was a surrogate marker of chronic inflammation, while in our studies, it corresponded to the severity of liver disease. The next most significant result of our research was that a higher level of platelets was detected in the blood of the experimental group of laboratory animals with liver damage and at the stage of the disease in the experimental group the average platelet content in the blood statistically increased to $437.50 \pm 18.53 \times 10$. The results of studies conducted on animals with a model of cirrhosis also established that with this pathology, the hemoglobin content in experimental animals of the main group decreased to 29.11% (38.34 g/l) and erythrocytes in cirrhotic animals decreased to $3.22 \pm 0.15 \times 10^{12}$ in 1 l, which is 33.88% lower than the value of a similar indicator in experimental animals of the intact group, which can serve as an indicator of the development of cirrhosis.

Conclusions: cirrhosis is a disease liver with a progressive inflammatory mechanism, which leads to the development of fibrosis, as well as the development of concomitant diseases in the liver. To prevent the consequences of this pathology, timely diagnosis of the presence and severity of liver damage is of particular importance. Experimental studies on animals with a CP model they proved that for liver cirrhosis diagnostic indicator is blood components.

References:

1. Tietge, U. J., Boker, K. H., Manns, M. P., & Bahr, M. J. (2004). Elevated circulating adiponectin levels in liver cirrhosis are associated with reduced liver function and altered hepatic hemodynamics. *American Journal of Physiology-Endocrinology and Metabolism*, 287(1), E82-E89.
2. Ginès, P., Krag, A., Abraldes, J. G., Solà, E., Fabrellas, N., & Kamath, P. S. (2021). Liver cirrhosis. *The Lancet*, 398(10308), 1359-1376.

3. Panasiuk, A., Zak, J., Kasprzycka, E., Janicka, K., & Prokopowicz, D. (2005). Blood platelet and monocyte activations and relation to stages of liver cirrhosis. *World Journal of Gastroenterology: WJG*, 11(18), 2754.
4. Уринов, А. М., Отожонов, И. О., & Ахмедова, Д. Б. (2022). Роль пробиотиков в лечении цирроза печени. *ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ СОҒЛИҚНИ САҚЛАШ ВАЗИРЛИГИ ТОШКЕНТ ТИББИЁТ АКАДЕМИЯСИ*, 37.
5. Ирискулов, Б. У., Абилов, П. М., Норбоева, С. А., Мусаев, Х. А., & Уринов, А. М. (2019). Современное состояние проблемы перекисного окисления липидов.
6. Рахимов, Б. Б., Уринов, А. М., Шайхова, Л. И., & Камилова, А. Ш. (2017). Выявление факторов риска при ожирении у детей дошкольного возраста, проживающих в г. Ташкенте.

